

Alexandrian Wicca

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Alexandrian Wicca is a branch of Gardnerian Wicca. It emerged in England in the 1960s and migrated to various parts of Scandinavia and continental Europe, USA, Canada, Australia and New Zealand. In this way, Alexandrian Wicca is a transnational movement.

Date Range: 1960 CE - 2025 CE

Region: Alexandrian Wicca

Region tags: Anglosphere, England

Transnational extent of Alexandrian Wicca

Status of Participants:

✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Hutton, Ronald. 2019. *The Triumph of the Moon : A History of Modern Pagan Witchcraft*. Second edition. ed. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Source 2: Adler, Margot. 1979. *Drawing down the Moon : witches, Druids, goddess-worshippers, and other pagans in America today*. New York: Viking Press.
- Source 3: White, Ethan Doyle. 2022. *Wicca: History, Belief and Community in Modern Pagan Witchcraft*. Eastbourne, Sussex.: Sussex Academic Press.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://alexandrianwitchcraft.org/all-articles/>

– Source 1 Description: Alexandrian Witchcraft Timeline & Archive website. This site is designed as a living, breathing, historical Timeline; an online meeting place where memories, lore and images can be shared and contributed.

– Source 2 URL: <https://www.britannica.com/topic/Wicca>

– Source 2 Description: General information on the broader subject of Wicca.

– Source 3 URL: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Alexandrian_Wicca

– Source 3 Description: Wikipedia entry for Alexandrian Wicca

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

– Source 1 URL: <https://alexandrianwitchcraft.org>

– Source 1 Description: Website devoted to Alexandrian Wicca

– Source 2 URL: <https://www.thewicca.co.uk>

– Source 2 Description: Website covering various traditions and personalities of Wica (Wicca)

– Source 3 URL: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Alexandrian_Wicca

– Source 3 Description: Wikipedia entry for Alexandrian Wicca

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: Gardnerian and Alexandrian Wicca often intersect within Europe, Scandinavia, Australia and New Zealand. Canada and the USA tends to maintain more separation. Alexandrian Wicca also interacts with Orders and groups dedicated to the practice of magic and occult arts.

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– No

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– Yes

↳ Assigned by class:

– No

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– No

↳ Assigned by gender:

– No

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– Yes

Notes: A ritual of initiation is conducted to assign religious affiliation. Inductees must be adults, generally 18 years or older.

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– No

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Does the religion have official political support

– No

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– I don't know

Notes: Detailed demographic data is not available.

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– I don't know

Notes: Detailed demographic data is not available.

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– No

Notes: Alexandrian Wicca has liturgy that practitioners can use, but not sacred writings.

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Is iconography present:

– Yes

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– At home

– Some public spaces

Notes: Participants frequently have iconographic representations of classical deities.

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):

– No

↳ Portrayals of afterlife:

– No

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):

– Yes

↳ Humans:

– No

↳ Other features of iconography:

– No

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body.

Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Reincarnation in this world:

– Yes

Notes: Open to personal interpretation but it is common for Alexandrian Wiccans to believe in reincarnation.

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Notes: Occasionally an Alexandrian Wiccan may be interred with personal goods, but it is not common.

Are formal burials present:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– No

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– I don't know

Notes: A subjective evaluation that cannot be applied to the whole religion.

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– No

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– Yes

Notes: A belief in the ancestors and their interest in the specific descendants,

either by blood or by choice.

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

Notes: The religion does not place any limits on what human spirits may know.

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

Notes: The religion does not place any limits on what human spirits may know.

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

Notes: The religion does not place any limits on what human spirits may know.

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– I don't know

Notes: The religion does not place any limits on what human spirits may know or do, or what they can see.

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– I don't know

Notes: The religion does not place any limits on what human spirits may know or do, or what they can see.

↳ Human spirit's can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– I don't know

Notes: The religion does not place any limits on what human spirits may know or do, or what they can see.

↳ Human spirits know your basic character (personal essence):

– I don't know

Notes: The religion does not place any limits on what human spirits may know or do, or what they can see.

↳ Human spirits know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– I don't know

Notes: The religion does not place any limits on what human spirits may know or do, or what they can see.

↳ Human spirits have other form(s) of knowledge regarding this world:

– I don't know

Notes: The religion does not place any limits on what human spirits may know or do, or what they can see.

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– I don't know

Notes: The religion does not place any limits on what human spirits may know or do, or what they can see.

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– I don't know

Notes: The religion does not place any limits on what human spirits may know or do, or what they can see.

↳ Human spirits have memory of life:

– I don't know

Notes: The religion does not place any limits on what human spirits may know or do, or what they can see.

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:

– I don't know

Notes: The religion does not place any limits on what human spirits may know or do, or

what they can experience.

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:

– I don't know

Notes: The religion does not place any limits on what human spirits may know or do, or what they can experience.

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

Notes: The religion believes that spirits may communicate with the living.

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

Notes: The religion believes that spirits may communicate with the living.

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

Notes: The religion believes that spirits may communicate with the living. Trance possession is a core component of the religion during its rituals.

↳ Through divination processes:

– Yes

Notes: Practitioners use a range of divinatory tools to engage with spirits.

↳ Only through specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Communicate with living through other means:

– I don't know

Notes: The religion believes that spirits may communicate with the living but does not place any limits on what human spirits may know or do, or what they can experience.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– I don't know

Notes: It is not widespread throughout the religion but it is believed some practitioners can see supernatural beings.

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– I don't know

Notes: It is not widespread throughout the religion but it is believed some practitioners can feel supernatural beings.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– I don't know

Notes: The religion does not place any limits on what human spirits may know or do, or what they can see.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– I don't know

Notes: The religion does not place any limits on what human spirits may know or do, or what they can see.

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– I don't know

Notes: The religion does not place any limits on what human spirits may know or do, or what they can express emotionally.

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– I don't know

Notes: The religion does not place any limits on what human spirits may know or do, or what they can express emotionally.

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– No

Notes: The religion does not record any instances of supernatural beings expressing hunger, although a small offering of food and drink can be made as a gesture of respect.

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: These supernatural beings can be psychically felt.

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– Yes

Notes: The religion includes the principle of the ancestors being present and aiding their descendants.

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– No

Notes: The religion does not structure the supernatural beings it engages with in a hierarchical model.

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural beings include deities and nature spirits.

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– Yes [specify]: Pantheons are structured according to the myths and legends that inspired them.

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– I don't know

Notes: There are too many variables for a simple answer to this question.

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– No

Notes: It is not a common belief for rewards to be bestowed in the afterlife.

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– No

Notes: It is not a primary consideration.

↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:

– No

Notes: This is a personal condition, some participants may seek political success through their practices but it is not common.

↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:

– I don't know

Notes: This is a personal condition, some participants may seek peace and social stability through their practices but it is not a feature of the religion.

↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:

– Yes

Notes: It is not a common activity, but healthy growth and good weather are both sought by some practitioners.

↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:

– I don't know

Notes: This is a personal condition but it is not a feature of the religion.

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– I don't know

Notes: This is a personal condition but it is not a feature of the religion.

↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– No

Notes: This is a personal condition but it is not a feature of the religion to seek extreme sensory pleasure.

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:

– No

Notes: This is a personal condition but it is not a feature of the religion.

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:

– No

Notes: This is a personal condition but it is not a feature of the religion.

↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:

– No

Notes: This is a personal condition but it is not a feature of the religion.

↳ Other [specify]

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– No

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– No

Notes: There is, however, a general agreement on maintaining ethical behaviour and good conduct within society.

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Notes: It is common for members to meet monthly for regular meetings, and every six weeks for seasonal meetings.

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Notes: Harming none is a key principle.

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

– Hours: 730

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– No

Notes: Members may choose to participate in large-scale rituals but it is not required.

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology universal:

– Yes

Notes: There may be exceptions but kinship terminology is common.

↳ Fictive kinship terminology widespread:

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon:

– No

Notes: There may be exceptions but kinship terminology is common.

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: A loosely connected international society that share some experiences and some cultural norms.

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– No

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– No

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– No

Notes: Informal education is available to those who wish to avail themselves of it, but it is not a formal process and those teaching do not generally hold a teaching qualification.

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– No

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– No

Notes: There is, however, generally an informal hierarchy within each group.

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– No

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The group's adherents are subject to the legal code in effect in the country in which they reside.

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Adherents are able to participate in institutionalised military at their own discretion. It is not a requirement, but nor is it prohibited.

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Some countries have a practice of conscription for military service.

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Notes: The common language is English.

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Educational establishments in each country promote understanding of written language.

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Educational establishments in each country promote understanding of written language.

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Notes: Alexandrian Wicca has a calendar based on (a) the lunar cycle, especially the full moon, and (b) eight seasonal festivals: spring and autumn equinox, summer and winter solstice, and four interspersed festivals.

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– No

Notes: Some adherents may undertake husbandry, farming, and hunting, but it is not a formal component of the religion.

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No